

Potentiometric Studies on Quaternary Complexes of Dioxouranium(VI) with Dibasic Acids

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Manuscript received 28 March 1977, accepted 21 November 1977

Formation of 1:1:1:1 quaternary complexes of dioxouranium(VI) ion with dibasic acids such as oxalic (OX), malonic (MALN), phthalic (PHA) and maleic (MA) acids has been inferred from pH metric studies and the stability constants of the resulting species have been evaluated.

As reported in the literature^{1,2} uranyl ion forms stable mixed ligand complexes in preference to simple binary complexes on the addition of more than one ligand. Thus the hydrolysis and polymerisation reactions of the simple 1:1 binary complexes exhibited on account of the available coordination sites of the central metal ion are postponed. The review of the literature reveals, although enough amount of work has been carried out on the ternary systems involving dioxouranium(VI) ion, only a few references are available on the quaternary systems³. It has, therefore, been considered of interest to carry out potentiometric investigations on some quaternary systems such as $UO_2-L-L'-L''$ where L, L' and L'' are the different dibasic acids. The results of these investigations are presented in this communication.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of BDH Analar grade. The stock solution of uranyl nitrate $UO_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ was prepared and the metal estimated gravimetrically as U_3O_8 .

The ligand solutions were prepared by direct weighing and the concentrations of the solutions were further checked by potentiometric titrations against 0.1 M KOH. The concentrations of the solutions (5×10^{-5} M in metal or ligand), total volume (50 ml) and ionic strength ($\mu = 0.1$ M KNO_3) were always kept constant at the beginning of the titration.

pH measurements were made with Philips precision pH meter (PR 9405 M) with accuracy ± 0.02 using standard glass (PV 9011) and calomel (PV 9021) electrodes. The instrument was standardized against 0.05 M potassium hydrogen phthalate (pH-4) at temperature $25 \pm 1^\circ$ before use.

Calculations :

The dissociation constants of dicarboxylic acids were determined by the method of Chaberek and Martell⁴ and the formation constant for the quaternary species by the method of Ramamoorthy and Santappa⁵

according to which

$$K_{ML'L''} = \frac{T_M - (1/3[A]X)}{(1/3^4[A]^4X)} \quad (T_M = T_L = T_{L'} = T_{L''})$$

$$\text{where } [A] = \frac{(2T_L + 2T_{L'} + 2T_{L''} - T_{OH} - [H])}{\frac{6[H]^2}{K_1 K_2 + K'_1 K'_2 + K''_1 K''_2} + \frac{3[H]}{K_2 + K'_2 + K''_2}},$$

$$(2T_L + 2T_{L'} + 2T_{L''} = 6T_M)$$

$$X = 1 + \frac{3[H]^2}{K_1 K_2 + K'_1 K'_2 + K''_1 K''_2} + \frac{3[H]}{K_2 + K'_2 + K''_2}$$

$T_M = \text{Total } [UO_2^{2+}]$, $T_L = \text{Total } [L]$, $T_{L'} = \text{Total } [L']$, $T_{L''} = \text{Total } [L'']$, $[A] = \text{Total free ligand concentration of L, L' and L''}$, $T_{OH} = \text{base consumed}$, $[H] = \text{free hydrogen ion concentration}$.

K_1 and K_2 , K'_1 and K'_2 and K''_1 and K''_2 are the first and second dissociation constants of the ligands L, L' and L'' respectively.

Results and Discussion

The curve representing the potentiometric titration of $UO_2(NO_3)_2$ with KOH is similar to that obtained by Feldman et al.⁵, sharp inflection obtained at $m = 2.3$ ($m = \text{moles of alkali added per mole of metal or ligand}$), being attributed to the formation of species such as $U_2O_8^{2+}$, $U_3O_8^{2+}$, $U_3O_8(OH)^+$, $U_3O_8(OH)_2$ etc.

Curve a representing the titration of 1:1 $UO_2(II)$ dibasic acid system exhibits inflections at $m \approx 2$ and $m \approx 4.5$. The first inflection at $m \approx 2$ ($pH = 3.5$) may be correlated to the formation of 1:1 $UO_2(II)$ -OX/MALN/PHA/MA complex, which, however, undergoes hydrolysis and polymerisation^{5,6} at higher pH. The second inflection at $m \approx 4.5$ may, probably, be attributed to the formation of the polynuclear species having U-O-U or $U \begin{matrix} \diagup OH \\ \diagdown OH \end{matrix} U$ groups.

Fig. 1.

The curve b representing the titration of uranyl ion in presence of isomolar amounts of two different acids exhibits inflections at $m \approx 4$ and $m \approx 5.5$. The first inflection may be ascribed to the formation of a 1:1:1 ternary species, whereas the second inflection at $m \approx 6.5$ may be attributed to the hydrolysis and polymerisation of the ternary species.

Curve c represent the titration of 1:1:1:1 quaternary system containing uranyl ion and three different dicarboxylic acid in equimolar ratio. The lowering in pH, non-appearance of a solid phase during the titration in the range of complexation and an inflection at $m \approx 6$ may be attributed to the formation of a 1:1:1:1 $\text{UO}_2\text{-L-L'-L''}$ species, which however, undergoes hydrolysis and polymerisation at higher pH, giving a second inflection at $m \approx 8.5$. The dissociation constants and formation constants are given in table 1 and 2 respectively.

TABLE 1

Ligand	pK_1^{a}	pK_2^{a}
Oxalic acid (OXH_2)	1.66	3.90
Malonic acid (MALNH_2)	2.75	5.36
Phthalic acid (PHAH_2)	2.89	5.04
Maleic acid (MAH_2)	2.23	5.97

TABLE 2

System	$\log K_{\text{MLL}\cdot\text{L}'\cdot\text{L}''}$
$\text{UO}_2\text{-OX-MALN-PHA}$	17.72 ± 0.25
$\text{UO}_2\text{-OX-MALN-MA}$	14.05 ± 0.30
$\text{UO}_2\text{-OX-PHA-MA}$	11.885 ± 0.16
$\text{UO}_2\text{-MALN-PHA-MA}$	16.19 ± 0.19

Acknowledgement

Authors' thanks are due to Dr. J.P. Tandon, Reader in Chemistry, Rajasthan University, Jaipur and Dr. R.C. Sharma, Chemistry Department, Agra College, Agra for their valuable suggestions. They also thank Agra College authorities for laboratory facilities and CSIR for granting a post doctoral fellowship to one of them (V.K.)

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